

ANNEXURE 2.5: Figures

Figure A2.5.1 (A to K): Consensus sequence profiles of the 11 prokaryotic organisms at their respective TSS regions, here ordinate represents the frequency of the nucleotide, while the nucleotide location (from -95 to +5 with TSS at 0) is shown on the abscissa.

Figure A2.5.1 A: *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens*

Figure A2.5.1 B: *Chlamydia pneumonia* CWL029

Figure A2.5.1 C: *Escherichia coli*

Figure A2.5.1 D: *Halofrex volcanii*

Figure A2.5.1 E: *Methanobolus psychrophilus*

Figure A2.5.1 F: *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H37Rv

Figure A2.5.1 G: *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* PA14

Figure A2.5.1 H: *Salmonella enterica* serovar Typhimurium

Figure A2.5.1 I: *Streptomyces coelicolor* A3

Figure A2.5.1 J: *Synechocystis* sp. PCC6803

Figure A2.5.1 K: *Thermococcus kodakarensis*

Figure A2.5.2 (A to K): Structure and energy profiles at TSS for 11 prokaryotic species. 1001 long TSS sequences from each organism were aligned (with TSS at 0th position) and were averaged. Likewise, all CDSs were arranged in a similar fashion. TSS sequence are shown in green, whereas red lines represent CDS. The numeric value of the parameter is represented by the ordinate, while the nucleotide position relative to TSS (at 0) is shown on the abscissa.

Figure A2.5.2 A: *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens*

Figure A2.5.2 B: *Chlamydia pneumoniae* CWL029

Figure A2.5.2 C: *Escherichia coli*

Figure A2.5.2 D: *Halofrex volcanii*

Figure A2.5.2 E: *Methanolobus psychrophilus*

Figure A2.5.2 F: *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H37Rv

Figure A2.5.2 G: *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* PA14

Figure A2.5.2 H: *Salmonella enterica* serovar Typhimurium

Figure A2.5.2 I: *Streptomyces coelicolor* A3

Figure A2.5.2 J: *Synechocystis* sp. PCC6803

Figure A2.5.2 K: *Thermococcus kodakarensis*

Figure A2.5.3: structure and energy profiles at TSS for the combined sequences from the 12 prokaryotic species using di-nucleotide data at their respective TSS regions. The numeric value of the parameter is represented by the ordinate, while the nucleotide position relative to TSS (at 0) is shown on the abscissa.

Figure A2.5.4 (A to G): Consensus sequence profiles of the 7 eukaryotic organisms at their respective TSS regions, here ordinate represents the frequency of the nucleotide, while the nucleotide location (from -80 to +20 with TSS at 0) is shown on the abscissa.

Figure A2.5.4 A: *Candida Albicans*

Figure A2.5.4 B: *Lachancea kluyveri*

Figure A2.5.4 C: *Naumovozya castellii*

Figure A2.5.4 D: *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*

Figure A2.5.4 E: *Saccharomyces paradoxus*

Figure A2.5.4 F: *Schizosaccharomyces pombe*

Figure A2.5.4 G: *Yarrowia lipolytica*

Figure A2.5.5 (A to K): Structure and energy profiles at TSS for 7 eukaryotic species. 1001 long TSS sequences from each organism were aligned (with TSS at 0th position) and were averaged. Likewise, all CDSs were arranged in a similar fashion. TSS sequence are shown in green, whereas red lines represent CDS. The numeric value of the parameter is represented by the ordinate, while the nucleotide position relative to TSS (at 0) is shown on the abscissa.

Figure A2.5.5 A: *Candida Albicans*

Figure A2.5.5 B: *Lachancea kluyveri*

Figure A2.5.5 C: *Naumovozyma castellii*

Figure A2.5.5 D: *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*

Figure A2.5.5 E: *Saccharomyces paradoxus*

Figure A2.5.5 F: *Schizosaccharomyces pombe*

Figure A2.5.5 G: *Yarrowia lipolytica*

Figure A2.5.6 (A to K): Structure and energy profiles at TSS for sequences from each chromosome from every eukaryote. 1001 long TSS sequences from each chromosome were aligned (with TSS at 0th position) and were averaged. Likewise, all CDSs were arranged in a similar fashion. TSS sequence are shown in green, whereas red lines represent CDS. The numeric value of the parameter is represented by the ordinate, while the nucleotide position relative to TSS (at 0) is shown on the abscissa.

Figure A2.5.6 A: *Candida albicans*

Chromosome 1:

Chromosome 2:

Chromosome 3:

Chromosome 4:

Chromosome 5:

Chromosome 6:

Chromosome 7:

Chromosome R:

Figure A2.5.6 B: *Kluyveromyces lactis*

Chromosome A:

Chromosome B:

Chromosome C:

Chromosome D:

Chromosome E:

Chromosome F:

Figure A2.5.6 C: *Lachancea kluyveri*

Chromosome A:

Chromosome B:

Chromosome C:

Chromosome D:

Chromosome E:

Chromosome F:

Chromosome G:

Chromosome H:

Figure A2.5.6 D: *Naumovozya castellii*

Chromosome 1:

Chromosome 2:

Chromosome 3:

Chromosome 4:

Chromosome 5:

Chromosome 6:

Chromosome 7:

Chromosome 8:

Chromosome 9:

Chromosome 10:

Figure A2.5.6 E: *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*

Chromosome I

Chromosome II

Chromosome III

Chromosome IV

Chromosome V

Chromosome VI

Chromosome VII

Chromosome VIII

Chromosome IX

Chromosome X

Chromosome XI

Chromosome XII

Chromosome XIII

Chromosome XIV

Chromosome XV

Chromosome XVI

Figure A2.5.6 F: *Schizosaccharomyces pombe*

Chromosome I

Chromosome II

Chromosome III

Figure A2.5.6 G: *Saccharomyces paradoxus*

Chromosome I

Chromosome II

Chromosome III

Chromosome IV

Chromosome V

Chromosome VI

Chromosome VII

Chromosome VIII

Chromosome IX

Chromosome X

Chromosome XI

Chromosome XII

Chromosome XIII

Chromosome XIV

Chromosome XV

Chromosome XVI

Figure A2.5.6 H: *Yarrowia lipolytica*

Chromosome A:

Chromosome B:

Chromosome C:

Chromosome D:

Chromosome E:

Chromosome F:

Figure A2.5.7: structure and energy profiles at TSS for the combined sequences from *C. elegans*. The numeric value of the parameter is represented by the ordinate, while the nucleotide position relative to TSS (at 0) is shown on the abscissa.

Figure A2.5.8 (A to F): Structure and energy profiles at TSS for sequences from each chromosome of *C. elegans*. 1001 long TSS sequences from each chromosome were aligned (with TSS at 0th position) and were averaged. Likewise, all CDSs were arranged in a similar fashion. TSS sequence are shown in green, whereas red lines represent CDS. The numeric value of the parameter is represented by the ordinate, while the nucleotide position relative to TSS (at 0) is shown on the abscissa.

Figure A2.5.8 A: Chromosome I

Figure A2.5.8 B: Chromosome II

Figure A2.5.8 C: Chromosome III

Figure A2.5.8 D: Chromosome IV

Figure A2.5.8 E: Chromosome V

Figure A2.5.8 F: Chromosome X

Figure A2.5.9 (A to X): Consensus sequence profiles obtained using Jalview at the intron to exon junction (ES sites) for the 51 nucleotide long sequences (ES at 26th position) from a randomly selected gene from each chromosome. Here ES sequences from a gene are aligned, and the consensus is derived. The lower panel of the figure represents the consensus and occupancy for each nucleotide.

Figure A2.5.9 A: Chromosome 1 (gene: AGTRAP)

Figure A2.5.9 B: Chromosome 2 (gene: ACTR3)

Figure A2.5.9 C: Chromosome 3 (gene: GYG1)

Figure A2.5.9 D: Chromosome 4 (gene: ANXA10)

Figure A2.5.9 E: Chromosome 5 (gene: IPO11)

Figure A2.5.9 F: Chromosome 6 (gene: ECT2L)

Figure A2.5.9 G: Chromosome 7 (gene: AEBP1)

Figure A2.5.9 H: Chromosome 8 (gene: ARHGEF10)

Figure A2.5.9 I: Chromosome 9 (gene: ASS1)

Figure A2.5.9 J: Chromosome 10 (gene: AKR1C1)

Figure A2.5.9 K: Chromosome 11 (gene: AKIP1)

Figure A2.5.9 L: Chromosome 12 (gene: ADGRD1)

Figure A2.5.9 M: Chromosome 13 (gene: CDC16)

Figure A2.5.9 N: Chromosome 14 (gene: AP4S1)

Figure A2.5.9 O: Chromosome 15 (gene: AGL1)

Figure A2.5.9 P: Chromosome 16 (gene: CORO1A)

Figure A2.5.9 Q: Chromosome 17 (gene: GOSR1)

Figure A2.5.9 R: Chromosome 18 (gene: CEP192)

Figure A2.5.9 S: Chromosome 19 (gene: AXL)

Figure A2.5.9 T: Chromosome 20 (gene: DLGAP4)

Figure A2.5.9 U: Chromosome 21 (gene: DYRK1A)

Figure A2.5.9 V: Chromosome 22 (gene: APOL1)

Figure A2.5.9 W: Chromosome X (gene: AR)

Figure A2.5.9 X: Chromosome Y (gene: DAZ2)

Figure A2.5.10 (A to X): Consensus sequence profiles obtained using Jalview at the exon to intron junction (EE sites) for the 51 nucleotide long sequences (EE at 26th position) from a randomly selected gene from each chromosome. Here EE sequences from the gene are aligned, and the consensus is derived. The lower panel of the figure represents the consensus and occupancy for each nucleotide.

Figure A2.5.10 A: Chromosome 1 (gene: ABL2)

Figure A2.5.60 B: Chromosome 2 (gene: AGPS)

Figure A2.5.10 C: Chromosome 3 (gene: APPL1)

Figure A2.5.10 D: Chromosome 4 (gene: ARHGAP24)

Figure A2.5.10 E: Chromosome 5 (gene: AFAP1L1)

Figure A2.5.10 F: Chromosome 6 (gene: AKAP7)

Figure A2.5.10 G: Chromosome 7 (gene: ADCY1)

Figure A2.5.10 H: Chromosome 8 (gene: APAT6)

Figure A2.5.10 I: Chromosome 9 (gene: ASS1)

Figure A2.5.10 J: Chromosome 10 (gene: ANTXRL)

Figure A2.5.10 K: Chromosome 11 (gene: ACTN3)

Figure A2.5.10 L: Chromosome 12 (gene: AEBP2)

Figure A2.5.10 M: Chromosome 13 (gene: CDC16)

Figure A2.5.10 N: Chromosome 14 (gene: ASPG)

Figure A2.5.10 O: Chromosome 15 (gene: AP4E1)

Figure A2.5.10 P: Chromosome 16 (gene: AMDHD2)

Figure A2.5.10 Q: Chromosome 17 (gene: ACBD4)

Figure A2.5.10 R: Chromosome 18 (gene: CTIF)

Figure A2.5.10 S: Chromosome 19 (gene: APOC1)

Figure A2.5.10 T: Chromosome 20 (gene: BTBD3)

Figure A2.5.10 U: Chromosome 21 (gene: USP16)

Figure A2.5.10 V: Chromosome 22 (gene: COMT)

Figure A2.5.10 W: Chromosome X (gene: CD99)

Figure A2.5.10 X: Chromosome Y (gene: CD99)

Figure A2.5.11 (A and B): structure and energy profiles at the ES and EE sites using dinucleotide data. The numeric value of the parameter is represented by the ordinate, while the nucleotide position relative to TSS (at 0) is shown on the abscissa.

Figure A2.5.11 A: Exon-Start

Figure A2.5.11 B: EE

Figure A2.5.12: Optimization of threshold value at μ , μ -SD and at μ -2SD for TSS in prokaryotes. The TSS vector is represented in green colour while the CDS vector is represented in red colour.

Figure A2.5.13: Optimization of threshold value at μ , μ -SD and at μ -2SD for TSS in eukaryotes. The TSS vector is represented in green colour while the CDS vector is represented in red colour.

Figure A2.5.14: Optimization of threshold value at μ , μ -SD and at μ -2SD for intron to exon transition (ES). The intron to exon transition vector is represented in green colour while the CDS vector is represented in red colour.

Figure A2.5.15: Optimization of threshold value at μ , μ -SD and at μ -2SD for exon to intron transition (EE). The exon to intron transition vector is represented in green colour while the CDS vector is represented in red colour.

